

AGING BEHAVIOR AND TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CAST AND SQUEEZED 6061-SiC PARTICLES COMPOSITES

Fatma.M.Fairouz¹, Atef.A.Daoud², Malak.T.Abou El-khair³

1 Researcher in Composite Materials Laboratory, CMRDI, Cairo, Egypt, f5fairoz@yahoo.com

2 Professor and head of Composite Materials Laboratory, CMRDI, Cairo, Egypt, adaoud_eg@yahoo.com

3 Professor in Composite Materials Laboratory, CMRDI, Cairo, Egypt, malak310@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

6061alloy based composites were prepared by stir casting method, followed by squeeze casting. The effect of squeeze casting on the aging behavior and tensile properties of 6061 reinforced with 5 vol. % SiC was investigated. Heat treatment was applied to the prepared composites and 6061 matrix alloy.

The samples were solution treated at 560 ° C for 2 hrs. aged at 177 ° C using different aging times to reach maximum hardness (T6-Tempr). Aging behavior was studied for the matrix and composites. The result revealed the formation of the peak of hardness as a result of GP zones (β'' (Mg_5Si_6)) and decreasing of hardness as a result of formation of β' ($MgSi > 1$). In addition, investigation of the interface between 6061 matrix and SiC reinforcements was carried out and indicated the formation of spinel ($MgAl_2O_4$) at the interface. Tensile properties of the composites were improved by application of squeeze casting process in comparison with the as cast matrix alloy and composites. Comparison squeezed composite with as cast composite and extruded matrix alloy, it has an increase of 133% of the 0.2% proof stress and 55% of the ultimate tensile stress for the as cast composite and an increase of ultimate tensile strength of 17% for the extruded matrix, demonstrating the excellent strengthening effect of SiC particles accompanied by squeeze casting. Fracture surfaces of the composites were investigated by SEM. Large number of micro-dimples was observed, which indicated the ductile fracture of the squeezed 6061 reinforced with SiC particles. The increase in the tensile properties may be due to mechanical interlock bonding produced between the matrix alloy and SiC by squeeze casting as well as a strong interfacial reaction product.

1 INTRODUCTION

In last decades metal matrix composites (MMCs) took their place as one of the most important engineering materials that were capable of providing good thermal and mechanical properties in addition to their light weight. The combination of low density and high strength to weight ratio as well as the ability to host various reinforcements makes aluminum and its alloys favorable materials for preparing MMCs. Actually, aluminum alloys of 6xxx series (Mg Si Al) have been used as matrix for many composites because they are heat treatable and wrought alloys. Therefore, many studies were conducted to study the effect of aging and plastic deformation on mechanical properties of 6xxx series matrix composites. [1, 2]. Applying of T6 heat treatment condition (solution treatment, quenching and artificial aging) leads the formation of Mg-Si precipitates, which improves the mechanical performance of 6061 alloy. The precipitation sequence is as follows:

Supersaturated solid solution \rightarrow clusters with varying Mg and Si contents \rightarrow G.P.zones (clusters with Mg and Si) \rightarrow β'' (Mg_5Si_6) \rightarrow β' ($Mg_{1.8}Si$) \rightarrow β (Mg_2Si). [3, 4]

Addition of particle reinforcements (SiC, Al_2O_3 , BC, etc....) may accelerate the precipitation kinetics of matrix alloy because the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between matrix alloy and ceramic reinforcements increases the dislocation densities that act as nucleation sites. [2, 3, 5, 6]

Squeeze casting is a hybrid metal processing technique that combines the advantages of both forging and casting in one step. In squeeze casting process, the molten metal solidifies under pressure

within closed dies positioned between plates of a hydraulic press. The applied pressure and instant contact of the molten metal with the die surface produce a rapid solidification that leads to the formation of a dense and fine grain structure as well as an improvement in the distribution of the particles in the matrix alloy, with good mechanical properties.[7] Also, the wettability between the molten metal matrix and the reinforcements is improved [8]. Therefore, the development in automotive industry stands up behind the development in squeeze casting researches to improve the mechanical properties of the produced components plus obtain a near net shape structure. In the present work, the effect of squeeze casting on aging behavior and tensile properties of the investigated materials were studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

In the current work, 6061 Al matrix was firstly prepared by melting the weighted parts of commercial pure aluminum and master alloys of Al-Si and Mg-Al in the crucible furnace. Chemical composition of prepared 6061 was detected by spectrophotometer, Table 1. SiC particles with size of 8 μ m were used. To overcome the problem of wettability between SiC particles and Al alloy, the particles were thermally activated by preheating them up to 900 ° C for 4 hrs. After complete melting, a vortex was carried out in the melt using a stainless steel impeller and the preheated SiC particles (5 vol. %) were added into the melt during the stirring, as shown in Fig.1. The prepared composite slurry (6061 Al matrix reinforced with 5 vol. % SiC) was poured in the metallic mold. The molten composite slurry at 800 ° C either for cast or squeezed casting was poured into preheated mold to 350 ° C. Subsequently, 150 MPa pressure was applied on the composite slurry using hydraulic press for loading time of 120 sec. Figure 2 shows the squeeze casting apparatus.

Figure 1: Schematic pattern for stir casting apparatus

Figure 2: Schematic pattern for squeeze casting hydraulic press

The prepared composite was solution treated at 560 ° C for 2 hrs. then water quenched. After that, the samples were aged at 177 ° C for several times and hardness was measured at different intervals of time to study the hardness – time aging behavior. Vickers hardness measurements were carried out using HBV-30A macrohardness tester. The mean hardness value of five readings was calculated for taken at load of 5Kgf. Samples were cut from the middle of the cast for metallographic investigations. Grinding of the specimens was carried out using different sizes of emery papers (120-1200) with continuous water. After grinding stages, polishing was carried out with alumina paste that was diluted with water using rotating disc covered with cloth. Specimens were etched with the ethyl alcohol+0.5% HF. Optical microscope examination was carried out by using Carlzise optical microscope. Scanning electron microscope examinations including microstructure, fracture surface and EDS to investigate the matrix/reinforcement interface were carried out by using Jeol JSM5410, Tensile test specimens were prepared according to ASTM standard. The length and diameter of gauge length were 20 and Φ 6.3 mm,

respectively. The tensile specimens were examined at rate of 0.5 mm/ min after subjected to heat treatment at T6 condition (solution treated at 560 °C for 2 hrs and aged at 177 °C for 10 hrs). Three tensile test specimens were done for matrix, cast and squeezed castings. The average values of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS), 0.2%yield stresses (Ys) and elongation was calculated. All the tests were conducted at room temperature using a screw driver universal testing machine (UH-F500KNI) at a crosshead speed of 05mm/min and applied load of 1000Kgf. In order to investigate the fracture mechanisms occurred in the different castings, the fracture surfaces of typical specimens subjected to tensile test were examined using SEM.

Alloy	Si%	Mg%	Al%
6061	0.854	1.33	Rest

Table 1: The chemical composition of prepared 6061 matrix

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 HEAT TREATMENT

Figure 3 illustrates the aging behavior of the prepared composites and matrix. At the beginning, hardness increased with increasing the time of aging for all specimens, region A. In region B, clusters with varying Mg and Si contents GP zones β'' (Mg_5Si_6) were formed. In BC region, formation of β' ($Mg_{1.8}Si$) is nearly complete. Region C, formation of β (Mg_2Si) is nearly complete and near completion of the artificial aging process (T6 temper). In CD region, dissolution of self-clusters of Mg was occurred, which resulted in decrease in volume fraction of strengthening phase β . [8].

Figure 3: Aging curve of prepared composites (cast and squeezed) and matrix

From Fig.3, the effect of addition of SiC particles on hardness is clearly observed. Hardness of 6061 composites is higher than that of the matrix. Also, composites reached to the maximum peak of hardness (~137 for cast and 150 Hv for squeezed composites) faster than matrix. It took 9 hours to reach the maximum hardness, while matrix took 20 hours as given in Table 2. The addition of SiC particles may results in generation of dislocation close to the aluminum matrix- SiC reinforcement interface.[10] This is due to the fact that the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the hard and brittle reinforcing particles and soft and ductile metal matrix results in elastic and plastic incompatibility between the matrix and the reinforcement.[11] Also, from Fig. 3, it can be concluded that both nucleation and growth of the GP zone are influenced by the addition of SiC particles. The precipitation kinetics are accelerated by adding the reinforcement. In other words, the time to reach the maximum hardness by the

aging treatment is reduced. The reason for the improvement of the kinetics of GP zone formation is related to the higher dislocation density of the metal matrix due to the thermal mismatch. This not only enhances the nucleation rate (heterogeneous nucleation), but also affects the diffusion rate of the solute elements. [12]

Alloy	Time to reach max. hardness (hrs)	Max. hardness Hv
Matrix (6061)	20	135
cast composite	9	137
Squeezed composite	10	150

Table 2: Max. hardness and time to reach it

Also, the effect of squeeze casting on the aging behavior can be observed. The squeezed composite exhibited higher hardness than that of cast composite (150 and 137 Hv respectively). This may be attributed to the hydraulic shock that encountered at the molten alloy, which causes the rapid heat transfer, thereby promoting rapid solidification. This leads to grain refining in squeeze cast composites, which improves hardness and mechanical properties.[7] In addition, application of external pressure on molten composites decreases the level of porosity.[13]

3.2 MICROSTRUCTURE

Microstructures of heat treated (T6) 6061 alloy and composite are presented in Fig. 4. It is observed from the Figure that the size of α -Al is decreased after both the addition of fine SiC and squeeze casting process, Fig.4 (b and d). The size of α -Al reduced from 200 μ m of matrix, to 100, 40 μ m) of cast and squeezed specimens, respectively. Application of external pressure during the solidification process increases the liquidus temperature of the alloy, which brings undercooling in superheated alloy, resulting in a finer grain size. [14] The final microstructure of 6061 Al alloy was affected by two main factors: addition of fine SiC and application of pressure during the process of solidification of the melt. Also, the microstructures of composite are shown in Fig.3 (c and e) indicate the uniform distribution of SiC particles and, despite, the existence of some clustering in some places. A strong interface between matrix and reinforcements is revealed from the microstructure of composite.

Figure 4: Microstructure of prepared 6061-5vol. %SiC, (a) matrix, (b, c) cast composite and (d, e) squeezed composite

3.3 INTERFACE ANALYSIS

Figure 5 (a and b) shows the EDX analysis at the interface between 6061 matrix alloy and SiC reinforcement particle, which indicates presence of Mg, Al and O₂ that may introduce a guide to formation of MgAl₂O₄ spinel at the interface as a reaction product during preparation of 6061 composite. Previous studies [15] have shown that the addition of a reactive metal such as Mg to the liquid aluminum accelerates the interaction with the ceramic particles. Additionally, it has been shown that Mg addition to aluminum lowers molten drop surface tension and its work of immersion in SiC [16]. Also, the peroxidation process of SiC particles enhances formation of SiO₂ layer on the particles [16]. During the composite preparation, the SiO₂ layer on the surfaces of SiC particles could react with Mg and Al in the matrix to form MgAl₂O₄ as shown in the following equations:

Figure 5: EDX analysis of SiC / matrix interface

In general, the interfacial reaction between ceramic and metal improves the wetting and / or bonding between the two constituent. The interfacial reactions would lead to a decrease in a dynamic wetting angle between reinforcement particles and matrix. Therefore, the formation of MgAl₂O₄ improved the wetting between SiC and matrix.

3.4 TENSILE PROPERTIES

Alloy 6061	YP-Stress (N/mm ²)	Max Stress (N/mm ²)	El.%
6061 extruded matrix	----	260 [17]	11[17]
cast composite	95	196	2
Squeezed composite	222	305	9

Table3: Tensile properties of extruded matrix [data from ref.17], cast and squeezed 6061 reinforced by 5vol. %SiC

The tensile properties of the 6061 extruded matrix, cast and squeezed SiC /6061 Al composite at T6 condition are shown in Table 3. Cast composite shows reasonable tensile properties with fracture strength of 196 MPa. However, squeezed composite exhibits excellent strength with strength of 305 MPa.

The squeezed composite attains an increase of 133% of the 0.2% proof stress and 55% of the ultimate tensile stress, demonstrating the excellent strengthening effect of both the SiC particles addition and the squeeze pressure. Comparing with extruded 6061 matrix as mentioned by Stefano et al. [17], the ultimate tensile strength of squeezed 6061 composite is greater with 17.3%, while the elongation decreases with 18%.

Figure 6: Scanning electron microscopy fractographs of (a) as cast 6061-5 vol.% SiC and (b, c) squeezed 6061-5 vol.% SiC

SEM fractographs of 6061 Al/ SiC composites are shown in Fig. 6(a-c) The effect of squeeze casting can be observed, Fig. 6(a) and (b), where fine and homogeneous fracture surface are clearly seen. The fracture surfaces are rough and uneven, and there are large quantities of micro-dimples that indicate some ductility, especially in case of squeezed 6061 reinforced with SiC particles. This is due to the strong bonding between the SiC particle and the matrix alloy produced by squeeze casting as well as the interfacial reaction. In composites, the fracture mechanism of SiC particles is controlled by the relationship between SiC particle strength and SiC /Al interface strength. A particle pull out will be the predominant mode if the particle strength is higher than SiC /Al interface strength , while a tensile loading induced SiC fracture will be the predominant if the interface strength is higher than the particle strength.

[18] As shown in Fig.5(c), a tensile loading induced SiC particles fracture occurred. SiC particles that covered with 6061 matrix (indicated by white arrows). The cleavage planes of SiC particles in ductile dimples are tightly surrounded by the Al matrix, exhibiting a characteristic of brittle fracture, which are circled by a white ellipse. This is because some remaining matrix layers are often found to adhere to the SiC particle surface, which indicates a stronger bonding strength between SiC /Al (marked with white arrows).

4 CONCLUSIONS

6061 Al alloy reinforced with 5vol.%SiC with size of 8 μm was prepared successfully by stir casting method followed by squeeze casting technique. Based on the results and discussion the following conclusions are drawn:

- The size of αAl is decreased after both addition of fine SiC and squeeze casting process
- The prepared composites have higher hardness value than that of the matrix and the squeeze pressure enhances the hardness value.
- Composites reached to the maximum peak of hardness faster than matrix, which means that the precipitation kinetics are accelerated by adding the reinforcement.
- Squeeze pressure increases the tensile strength of heat treated 6061 based composite. Increase of 133% of the 0.2% proof stress and 55% of the ultimate tensile stress is achieved, demonstrating the excellent strengthening effect due to the SiC particle additions.
- The microstructure of composite reveals a uniform distribution of SiC particles and a good interface between matrix and reinforcements
- From the EDX analysis results at the interface between 6061 matrix alloy and SiC particle, it can be concluded that MgAl_2O_4 spinel has been formed as a reaction product during preparation of 6061 based composites
- The fracture surfaces are rough and uneven, and there are large quantities of micro-dimples in case of squeezed 6061 reinforced with SiC particles. The fracture mechanism is a tensile loading induced SiC particles fracture, which indicates a strong bonding strength of SiC/Al interface.

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